

The use of games in the teaching of Production Engineering: a list based on publications in Scopus

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Abstract

The use of games in the teaching of production engineering is on the rise since it allows the presentation of knowledge and its absorption in a more relaxed way, it helps the development of essential skills for a good professional as well. As a way of identifying educational games developed, used and/or published in production engineering courses, a qualitative research was carried out on the Scopus database. The research returned 40 publications, of which 11 could not be accessed and only 18 had games related to the course in question. As a result, 44 games were compiled, which were listed in order to facilitate their knowledge by teachers in the area, stimulating their application and the modernization of teaching.

Keywords: Educational Games; Production Engineering; Game-based Learning; Game List.

1 Introduction

The advancement of technologies, the dynamics of the modern world, the sharing of information in real time, the adaptation needs, among other issues, caused the students' profile to be significantly changed (RUBEUS, 2021).

In this way, the traditional teaching-learning strategies are no longer sufficient for this profile that seeks more condensed and faster information. Evidence of this fact is that much has been studied and developed in relation to active methodologies.

The active learning methodology is any educational approach in which students actively participate in the learning process, becoming the centrepiece of the process and the main responsible for their learning (Lázaro et al., 2018). They encourage debates and practice, as well as the review of knowledge through explanations with other students. Some of the main active methodologies are: Project-Based Learning, Problem-Based Learning, Gamification, Game-Based Learning (GBL).

With the world increasingly dynamic, the GBL has proved to be a good teaching tool, since it uses games to generate greater engagement, motivate action, promote learning or solve problems in a creative way, in the case of an excellent way to help students lose resistance in the face of complex topics (Sales et al., 2017).

It turns out that the application of games implies the need for development or knowledge of the existence of the game on the part of the teacher as well as in its study. Although the absence of games was a problem a few years ago, today there are already several games that can be applied in teaching different subjects and courses. However, finding a game suited to a specific subject, discipline or competence is often hard work that inhibits the adoption of the GBL (Bonetti, 2014).

In order to facilitate and encourage the use of games in the teaching of Production Engineering, this research presents a list of games found in national and international publications.

2 Methods

This bibliographic research was carried out by searching the titles of Scopus publications, using the following keywords: game AND engineer* AND (product* OR manufact* OR industrial). The search resulted in 40

publications, of which 11 could not be accessed and only 18 had games related to Production Engineering. After analysing the publications found, 44 games were identified.

Although it would be desirable to present a detailed description of the games, including the number of players, application time, the skills worked, among others, the lack of standardization in the data presented limited the study to presenting few characteristics (name, description, access, format and areas/subjects addressed), listed in table 1.

Therefore, this is a bibliographical, qualitative and exploratory research that aims to identify games that can be used in Production Engineering courses.

3 Researches about the use of games

The use of games as a tool to help teach specific content in the classroom is not a new idea (HILL et al., 2003). Education scholars, such as Vygotsky (1989) and Piaget (1972), present games as extremely important tools for the development of cognitive skills, especially in early childhood and elementary education. Through them, the child acts and has his/her creativity stimulated, in addition to acquiring self-confidence and concentration. These same opinions are reinforced by Macedo et al. (2008), according to whom, in addition to promoting cognitive development, "playing" is engaging, interesting and stimulating.

Even though much of the initial research was focused on early childhood and elementary school, today there is already a lot of research on the use of games in higher education. Bahadoorsingh, Dyer and Sharma (2016) states that games provide a different pedagogical perspective within a higher education context. Although they may not seem natural, they represent two critical factors that need to be considered: they are impactful and they are emerging as a potential source of disruption in current teaching models.

To be an educational game, games need to be focused on teaching a certain subject, expanding concepts and improving some skills and attitudes that players/students seek/acquire during the game (Dempsey et al., 1996). The use of games for pedagogical purposes has grown and covered several areas, from health (Alloni et al., 2017; Pires et al., 2019), resource management (Bellotti et al., 2014; Othman et al., 2016) and even learning new languages (Eltahir et al., 2021).

Several authors such as Kishimoto (2004) and McDowell et al. (2006) reinforce the importance of the game as a great motivator and facilitator so that concepts can be absorbed more quickly and dynamically. On the other hand, Bonetti (2014) reports that game development is arduous and costly, which makes it difficult for teachers to perform them, who need to resort to existing games. According to the author, there are no specific environments for searching games for educational purposes, these "are scattered on the Internet in a non-centralized way, without a systematic and uniform representation of their relevant information", which makes the search time-consuming, complicated and not very efficient.

From this difficulty arises this research, which identified and listed some games used in the teaching of Production Engineering, in order to facilitate access to games by interested parties.

4 Results: a list of games for Production Engineering

At first, more than 20 items were defined to describe the characteristics of the games found. However, the lack of standardization and information meant that only 5 items were presented here, because only these fields could be filled in, for at least 50% of the games listed.

The listed features are:

- **Name:** the game's title;
- **Description:** brief description of the game based on information provided in publications;
- **Access:** informs the type of access, whether the game can be accessed freely (free), paid or trial (free to test, but pay to use), also indicates if the game is available or if it is for internal use only /specific;
- **Format:** indicates whether the game is physical or digital;

- **Areas:** indicates the areas that are worked on by the game, such as: management, marketing, life cycle, etc.

Characteristics that can be considered important for pedagogical purposes, such as: subjects in which games are usually used, number of players/teams, time required to apply the games, etc., were not listed due to lack of information.

The reference work(s) used in the research were included in the results. Table 1 presents the games identified and applicable to the Production Engineering course.

Table 1 – List of games applied to Production Engineering and their characteristics.

Name	Description	Access	Format	Area(s)	Cited by
(not indicated - ETO SIM)	A simulation game that involves product lifecycle planning in an Engineer-To-Order (ETO) environment.	-	Digital	life cycle, LCA	Gutiérrez & Sastrón (2009)
(not indicated)	A virtual reality game in which players "visit" an industrial environment and need to identify various elements and concepts, as well as establish hypotheses and models.	-	Digital	manufacturing systems	Urigo et al. (2022)
(not indicated)	A computer simulation game between juice companies.	-	Digital	business management	Braghirolli et al. (2016)
Beer game	A board game that already has a digital version and that simulates the beer supply chain.	-	Physical and Digital	supply chain management, bullwhip	Despeisse (2019), Machado et al. (2021)
Bernard - Industrial Simulator	A business game in the consumer durables sector that reproduces operating conditions of the main functional areas of an industry. For each simulated period it is necessary to plan the machines, facilities and raw materials needed, human resources.	Paid	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Igidio et al. (2017), Ishihara, Neto & Neumann (2021)
BEWARE Game	A risk management simulation game.	-	Digital	risk management	Hauge & Riedel (2012)
Business Game	A business game used in Young Business Talents (an international competition) whose objective is to analyze, plan and control a company.	Free	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Igidio et al. (2017)
Business Management	A business game in the area of microcomputers.	Paid	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Ishihara, Neto & Neumann (2021)
Cesim Firm	A business game in the pharmaceutical industry that integrates the functional areas of production, marketing and logistics, helping participants to plan their strategies and practice decision making, having interactions between all typical functions within the company.	Paid	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Igidio et al. (2017), Ishihara, Neto & Neumann (2021)
CityCar	A dynamic simulation game related to the development of new products in which teams of 5 to 7 players compete against each other.	-	Physical	product development	Despeisse (2019), Kerga et al. (2014)
COSIGA	A simulation game focused on simultaneous engineering in which players must develop a truck (construction, mobile home or delivery).	Free	Digital	product development	Kerga et al. (2014), Hauge & Riedel (2012), Riedel, Pawar & Barsonn (2001)
Factory Heroes	A cooperative RPG-style board game that works on sustainable management in a manufacturing company.	-	Physical	sustainability	Despeisse (2019)
Fishbanks	A board game that already has a digital multiplayer version in teams that represent fishing companies and need to maximize their profits while competing for natural resources.	Paid	Physical and Digital	resource management, sustainability	Despeisse (2019)
Furniture Factory	A computer simulation game that works basic concepts of production engineering for freshmen through a scenario referring to a furniture company.	-	Digital	manufacturing systems management, Production Engineering concepts	Bengoa et al. (2013)

Name	Description	Access	Format	Area(s)	Cited by
Production Game (Game da Produção)	A mobile game developed specifically for the Production Engineering course at UnB, in which students can simulate their trajectory through the course, understanding the disciplines and activities that must be carried out until completion.	-	Digital	Education	Júnior, Simão Monteiro & Madeira Campos (2019)
General Management	A business game in the field of graphic design industry.	Paid	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Ishihara, Neto & Neumann (2021)
Production Management (Gestão da Produção 1 -GP-1)	A business game whose objective is to determine the quantity of products to be produced in normal and extended hours and how much of the production must be outsourced, so that the profit is maximum.	-	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Igidio et al. (2017)
GLOTRAN	A computer simulation game that simulates the development and production of a product across different teams.	-	Digital	product development	Kerga et al. (2014)
GSim - Goldratt Simulator	A simulator used as a game to work concepts of Theory of Constraints (TOC)	Free	Digital	production management, theory of constraints	Machado et al. (2021)
Industrial Simulator	A business game in the area of physical goods.	Paid	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Ishihara, Neto & Neumann (2021)
Industrial Strategic Simulator	A business game in the area of physical goods.	Paid	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Ishihara, Neto & Neumann (2021)
JOGAI - The Industrial Engineering Undergraduate Game	A game that simulates the supply chain of gemstones and jewelry through group dynamics, with assembly of parts in which different companies compete with each other.	-	Physical	planning and control	Barçante et al. (2011)
LCA Game	An RPG-style computer simulation game that focuses on analyzing the environmental impact of the company's coffee machine production.	-	Digital	life cycle, LCA	Despeisse (2019)
Lean Board Game	A board game that simulates the operation of an industry allowing the monitoring of various indicators.	-	Physical	production management	Machado et al. (2021)
LSSP_PCP*	A business game in which the simulated company produces three different families of meshes, with sectors of Knitwear. Dyeing and Finishing. It is necessary to manage the company that has variable demand.	Free	Digital	demand forecast	Igidio et al. (2017)
Moto Cycle	A business game in the area of motorcycle industry.	Paid	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Ishihara, Neto & Neumann (2021)
NCTB GAME	A business (computerized) game in which students must make weekly decisions related to different areas (purchasing, production, quality control and marketing) of a packaging company in order to obtain the best possible results.	Paid	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Bringelson et al. (1995)
One thousand kWh	A card game in which the highest score is sought, which is obtained by reducing the energy saved in the company's plant.	-	Physical	sustainability	Despeisse (2019)
Production Management – PM	A business game in the field of furniture industry.	Free	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Ishihara, Neto & Neumann (2021)
Production Planning Simulation – PPS	A business game in the area of fictional products.	Paid	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Ishihara, Neto & Neumann (2021)
Production System Simulation Laboratory – PSSL	A business game in the area of knitting industry.	Free	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Ishihara, Neto & Neumann (2021)
SBCE game	A dynamic simulation game in which players must develop a simplified aircraft structure respecting the established parameters, using two different proposals (PBCE and SBCE).	-	Physical	product development, lean	Kerga et al. (2014)

Name	Description	Access	Format	Area(s)	Cited by
Strategic Simulation (SDE <i>Simulação Estratégica</i>)	A business game in which participants plan and implement a new venture that will produce and market the RPB – Portable Beverage Refrigerator – a new product, without equal, competing with other simulated companies in different markets. At the end of the simulation, the performance of the groups is evaluated based on the analysis of the results obtained.	Paid	Digital	entrepreneurship	Igidio et al. (2017)
Simulators and Management Models (SDG – <i>Simuladores e modelos de gestão</i>)	An interactive business simulation applied in the Global Management Challenge (international strategy and management competition) in which each team manages a company with the objective of obtaining the best investment performance for their company in the market in which it operates.	Paid	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Igidio et al. (2017)
Shoe Maker	A business game in the shoe industry.	Paid	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Ishihara, Neto & Neumann (2021)
Simulare	A business game in which teams compete with each other, having to make decisions such as price, investment in advertising, receipt and payment terms, purchases of inputs and machinery, hiring and firing of personnel, loans, financing, etc.	Paid	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Igidio et al. (2017), Ishihara, Neto & Neumann (2021)
Production Planning Simulation (SPP <i>Simulação de Planejamento da Produção</i>)	A business game in which participants act as leaders of an industrial unit, that produces VERIPEX (fictitious product), which must be shipped according to the quantity requested by the customer. Participants must make strategic and managerial production decisions, simulating results, in quarterly cycles. Who accumulates the highest net profit at the end of the 4th period wins the game.	Paid	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Igidio et al. (2017)
Supply Chain and Channel Management	A business game in the area of microcomputers.	Paid	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Ishihara, Neto & Neumann (2021)
TFC business game (The Fresh Connection)	A computer simulation of a supply chain that must be optimized.	-	Digital	simulation, operational research, production, quality, logistics	Mosia (2018)
The Product Line Planning Game	A game in the form of dynamics that brings consumers and developers together by facilitating the presentation of consumer requirements and feedback to developers. As a result of the matches are scenarios/stories that help in the development of projects.	-	Physical	agile method	Carbon et al. (2008)
The Trimrian Factory Game	A dynamic simulation game that depicts a bankrupt company trying to get back on its feet by fulfilling a customer's orders within 6 rounds.	-	Physical	production	Jensen (2008)
Topaz Management Simulation	A business game with 3 different product options.	Paid	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Ishihara, Neto & Neumann (2021)
Virtonimics Enterprenuer	A business game in the clothing field.	Paid	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Ishihara, Neto & Neumann (2021)
Virtual Business Retailing	A business game in the grocery/convenience store area.	Paid	Digital	production, finance, marketing and logistics	Ishihara, Neto & Neumann (2021)

Source: Authors (2022)

Even performing a very limited search, it could be noted that part of the publications found in the research were not aligned with the scope of this work. Among them is the article by Zhou (2018) that analyses the scenario of the chemical industry through game theory. Another article that was discarded, although it presented an analysis of publications in the area of games for Production Engineering, was that of Rosado and

de Souza (2021), since the authors carried out a bibliographic mapping, without it being possible to identify any game.

Contrary to Rosado and de Souza (2018) are the works of Despeisse (2018), Igidio et al. (2017), Ishihara, Netto and Neumann (2021) and Kerga et al. (2014) which present game relationships with different approaches. Despeisse (2018) analyses 6 (six) games and relates them to the cognitive development domains of Bloom's Taxonomy. Igidio et al. (2017) succinctly present 8 (eight) business games and an applied study of the Management of Production 1 (GP-1), Ishihara, Netto and Neumann (2021) present 16 business games from the analysis of their manuals, bringing information internals of the games and Kerga et al. (2014) cites three games related to product development and analyses and presents the results of applying another game in the area. The games that were only mentioned by these authors are listed in this research, although they have little general information.

The scarcity of information caused the work of Scholl, Gube and Koppatz (2021) to be disregarded, since the authors report the development of two physical games (Social Engineering Theater and Risk Roulette) that could not be properly tested due to the Covid-19 pandemic.

5 Conclusion

This research aimed to present a list of games that can be used in Production Engineering teaching, making the teaching-learning process more motivating and effective. As a result, 44 games were found and listed.

There was a lack of standardization in the obtained data. which makes it difficult to properly and quickly evaluate and access the games. The absence of information on locations and access methods also prevents verifying whether the games are really active. This lack of information implies the need to seek new materials so that there is better detail and more direct guidance to readers who are interested in making use of games in their classes.

This research emerged as part of a larger research which aims to establish a methodology for identifying and making available information of games that facilitate their discovery and application by teachers and other interested parties. In general, the lack of standardized information that describes games as a learning object is something that has been studied, with researches related to the adoption of metadata standards, such as the Learning Object Metadata (from the IEEE) and the Dublin Core (DC). This adoption becomes necessary so that works like this can be more meaningful, bringing more relevant and updatable information.

As future research, a deeper analysis of the identified games is suggested in order to update the information and present only games that are active and accessible (free of charge or for a fee) to the public, since it is believed that a good part of the games listed here are not available or are already obsolete, as in the case of The Product Line Planning Game (Carbon et al. 2008) which either must have undergone an update, or has already left the market, since it used floppy disks.

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